

Integrated Quality Assurance and Control Framework for BIM Models during Design, Construction and Operation

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Abstract

Implementing BIM in the Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) industry has reinvented this sector's business model, changing the traditional way of handling projects. This transformation had a significant impact on collaboration and data communication. However, the digital transition brought up numerous questions about Quality Management in this new setting.

The BIM model has taken a central role in the digital environment. With all essential information within the model, the quality of the model became crucial, meaning that any deficiencies can cause significant consequences, impacting the overall collaboration process. As a result, the reliability of the whole project depends directly on the integrity of the model in terms of quality. Despite the variety of model checking tools available on the market, there is a lack of an integrated approach to Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) that would support project delivery from its commencement to handover, considering the defined BIM uses, requirements and acknowledging industry data and standards. This work

discloses existing methodologies and provides a review of the guidelines and tools addressing QA/QC on the market.

The primary concern in achieving model quality lies in assuring that the model contains all needed information and aligns with the requirements defined by the appointing parties. However, research shows that inadequate definitions of requirements and the model's compliance to these requirements, present one of the biggest obstacles to effective collaboration of clients and appointed parties. This study focuses on exploring currently used methods of specifying requirements while seeking improvement solutions. To bridge this gap, this research proposes a comprehensive QA/QC methodology designed to guarantee model compliance with the appointing party's specific requirements. The primary objectives are threefold: first, creating a tool that addresses QA during the model creation process; second, the QC verification procedures integrated into the proposed methodology; and third, exploring the possibilities of automation. Furthermore, this study lays the groundwork for future research on enhancing the model quality by focusing on automating the requirements specification.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/qkNRzpmvgqE>

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